

Anti-diabetic Potential of Cyanidin-3-O-glucoside versus PPAR δ Synthetic Agonist GW2433: An In-Silico Approach

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Abstract

In the quest for effective diabetes mellitus (DM) treatment strategies, oral antidiabetic medications that are agonists of peroxisome proliferator-activated receptors (PPARs) have demonstrated potential. However, the growing frequency of adverse effects associated with many existing treatments has highlighted the need for new and safer solutions. Due of PPAR δ 's critical role in the pathophysiology of Type II diabetes mellitus, attempts to find new compounds that target T2DM. This work examines the antidiabetic potential of cyanidin-3-O-glucoside (C3G), an anthocyanin found in berries, as potential PPAR δ agonists utilizing a multimodal approach that combines pharmacophore analysis, pharmacokinetic evaluation, and in-silico molecular docking. According to molecular docking, C3G has a higher binding affinity ($\Delta G = -8.9$ K cal/mol) than synthetic fibrate GW2433 ($\Delta G = -8.4$ K cal/mol). Additional pharmacophore/ADMET profiling study confirms that C3G's drug-likeness is better in comparison to synthetic fibrate GW2433. The results indicate that the phytochemical C3G has potential as a PPAR δ agonist. This molecule may be a safer and more effective candidate for novel antidiabetic medications after additional experimental validation.

Keywords : Molecular docking, ADMET profiling, Bioactive phytochemicals, cyanidin-3-O-glucoside, GW2433, PPAR δ agonists.

1.0 Introduction

Diabetes is a serious, chronic disease characterized by elevated blood glucose concentrations related to the effects of abnormal β -cell biology on insulin action. Notably, over 90% of those affected with type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM) [1]. Diabetes facts and figures show the growing global diabetes burden for individuals, families and countries. The latest International Diabetes Federation (IDF) Diabetes Atlas (2025) reports that 11.1% – or 1 in 9 – of the adult population (20-79 years) is living with diabetes, with over 4 in 10 unaware that they have the condition of T2DM. By 2050, projections show that 1 in 8 adults, approximately 853 million, will be living with diabetes, an increase of 46% [2]. In the early stages of T2DM, insulin demand increases due to peripheral insulin resistance, when the body compensates by stimulating islet β cells to release more insulin, thereby maintaining blood glucose stability. However, in the later stages, impaired islet β cell function due to prolonged hyperglycaemia causes the absolute deficiency of insulin in the body [3], and insulin remains the first-line treatment for T2DM.

The current therapeutic strategies include oral hypoglycaemic medications such as insulin secretagogues, incretin agonists, insulin sensitizers, dipeptidyl peptidase-4 inhibitors, and α -glucosidase inhibitors. These methods aim to achieve a controlled blood glucose level, however there are issues with their accessibility, price, and recognized side effects, such as gastrointestinal distress, lactic acidosis, and hypoglycaemia [4-6]. Medicinal plants have a major role in human pharmacological formulations for both prevention and treatment of T2DM. Herbal medicine is the only affordable medical treatment available, especially for the most impoverished individuals [7]. Therefore, finding appropriate methods to regulate insulin levels in the body may provide new and effective means for the treatment. Herbal remedies are also gaining popularity in both developed and developing countries due to its high quality, safety, efficacy, few side effects, and accessibility. Some of the existing drugs, such as aspirin, digitalis, quinine (an anti-malarial), vincristine, and vinblastine (an anti-cancerous), are derived from plant sources. Plant-based phytochemicals are effective against oxidative stress, cancer chemotherapy, blood disorders, brain disorders, cardiovascular illnesses, diabetes, microbes, inflammation, and reproductive

issues [8]. According to recent studies, the risk of diabetes can be mitigated by including the appropriate herbs in our diet and practicing good nutritional control [9].

The transcription factor peroxisome proliferator-activated receptor (PPAR), which includes three isoforms: PPAR α , PPAR γ , and PPAR β/δ , has been reported to be involved in a variety of physiological processes, including glucose and lipid metabolism, insulin resistance, and anti-inflammatory effect [10]. Among them, the PPAR β/δ subtype is considered to be an important pharmacological target for the treatment of diabetes and its related diseases in many studies. For example, PPAR β/δ deficient mice exhibit obesity and glucose intolerance under a high-fat diet [11]. PPAR β/δ can also become a promising treatment for patients with diabetes nephropathy through its downstream signal transduction [12]. Current therapies for T2DM involve regulating hormones [13,14] and utilizing bioactive substances from natural plants [15,16]. Cyanidin-3-O-glucoside, also known as Kuromanin, is one of the most important anthocyanins in nature. For instance, cyanidin-3-O-glucoside (C3G), an anthocyanin in berries, reduces body weight and improves metabolic homeostasis in mice by altering hepatic FGF21[17]. In addition, research has demonstrated that C3G can prevent diabetic nephropathy in rats through the regulation of relevant hormones in vivo [18]. It inhibits different enzymes involved in central nervous system pathologies and type-2 diabetes and has demonstrated to be a candidate as enzyme inhibitor with neuroprotective, antioxidant and antidiabetic potential [19]. However, there are few studies on whether C3G can ameliorate T2DM by regulating insulin release and its potential mechanisms for PPAR δ receptors.

In the present study, anti-diabetic, activities of C3G molecule have been investigated and compared with the synthetic fibrate GW2433 (a potent chemical compound, specifically a dual agonist for PPAR α and PPAR δ receptors), used in scientific research for studying metabolic diseases like type II diabetes and dyslipidemia by mimicking natural fatty acids to regulate glucose and lipid metabolism.

2.0 Materials and methods

2.1 Protein and Ligand preparation

The crystal structure of peroxisome proliferator-activated receptor delta (PPAR δ) (PDB ID: 1GWX) was retrieved from Protein Data Bank (PDB) repository [20] in pdb format. A chain of the protein was saved removing water and other part of the protein using BIOVIA Discovery Studio Visualizer software [21] and finally prepared with Autodock Tools- incorporated with PyRx Software [22]. Cyanidin-3-O-glucoside (PubChem CID:441667) and GW2433 (PubChem CID:1517) molecule, were obtained from PubChem [23] in 3D.sdf format and further minimized and converted into PDBQT format with PyRx software. A Chain of PPAR δ (PDB ID: 1GWX) with binding site and structure of the both the molecules are shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. A Chain of PPAR δ (PDB ID: 1GWX) with Binding Site and structure of C3G and GW2433

2.2 Protein-ligand docking

The docking calculations were performed using the AutoDock Vina software suite incorporated with PyRx. Flexible Blind docking was performed by applying a gridbox (x: 27.3721, y: 8.2958 and z: 65.1809 and dimensions (in Å^0) x: 54.0980, y: 46.1842, z: 58.5983 to cover the whole protein with an exhaustiveness value of 9. The contributions of intramolecular hydrogen bonds, hydrophobic, ionic, and Van der Waals interactions between docked protein and ligand complexes were used to determine the free energy (ΔG) specifying affinity scoring of the binding. After docking best pose (with zero lower and upper rmsd value) was chosen for further analysis. The docked protein-ligand complexes were created and the binding sites were analyzed to construct a 2D and 3D representation of the ligand interaction for each complex using BIOVIA Discovery Studio Visualizer software.

2.3 Screening of Ligand for Pharmacokinetics and Drug-Likeness

Candidate molecules are identified as drug molecules based on their pharmacokinetics and toxicity. Chemicals' absorption, distribution, metabolism, excretion, and toxicity (ADMET) have been identified as critical factors in the early phases of computer-aided drug design (CADD). The SwissADME [24] Web tool was used to evaluate the Pharmacokinetics, drug-likeness, and medicinal chemistry of these molecules. The SMILES format of the molecules was entered, and 2D structure files were generated. Several parameters were analyzed to check the ADMET properties of these molecules. Important parameters for a drug molecule include pharmacokinetics parameters like P-glycoprotein, HIA (human intestinal absorption), drug-likeness prediction Lipinski, Ghose, and Veber criteria, and the BBB (Blood-Brain Barrier penetration). In order to evaluate drug-likeness, a number of additional crucial parameters were employed, including molecular weight, LogP, number of HBA and HBD, as well as the Lipinski, Ghose, and Veber guidelines. Most "drug-like" compounds have $\log P \leq 5$, molecular weight (MW) ≤ 500 , number of hydrogen bond acceptors (nHA) ≤ 10 , and number of hydrogen bond donors (nHD) ≤ 5 , according to Lipinski's "Rule of 5" [25]. If a molecule violates multiple principles, it might face issues with its bioavailability. The human intestinal absorption, bioavailability, Caco-2 (human epithelial colorectal adenocarcinoma cell line), monolayer permeability, and blood-brain barrier penetration can all be described by the ideal descriptor, LogP (octanol/water partition coefficient), Topological Polar Surface Area (TPSA). These factors play a significant role in predicting the qualities of drug.

3.0 Results and Discussion

3.1 Molecular docking and Analysis of molecular interactions

Molecular docking (virtual screening) provides a quick, reliable, and economical method for finding new medications (lead compounds) and possible druggable protein targets. In this work, we used virtual screening based on molecular docking to identify a potential target for Type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM). Following a comprehensive literature review and considering available crystal structures of proteins pivotal in T2DM's biosynthetic pathways, we have selected peroxisome proliferator-activated receptor delta (PPAR δ) (PDB ID: 1GWX). The probable molecular docking interactions between ligand C3G and A chain of the PPAR δ were examined in this in-silico study. The results were compared to GW2433, a synthetic fibrate. In comparison to GW2433's binding energy of -8.4 kcal/mol, C3G showed greater binding energies of -8.9 kcal/mol (Table 1). The ligand or inhibitor's binding affinity (Kcal/mol) is a parameter that may be correlated and examined with the relevant protein target. A greater affinity (more negative) of the ligand for the receptor protein is typically indicated by a lower binding energy. As a result, the ligand exhibiting the highest affinity becomes a potential candidate deserving of additional investigation.

In our investigation ligand C3G binds with A chain of 1GWX with four hydrogen bonds with residues Met228, Glu291, Thr292 and Asn343. The molecule GW2433 also binds with four hydrogen bonds with residues Gly261, Thr288, Ala342, Ser345, but with lower Binding Affinity. These whole findings are summarized in Table 1. Fig. 2a- 3b depicts the 3D and 2D diagrams of different phytochemicals showing H-bond donor and receptor regions with bindings of residues in active sites of the A chain of the protein 1GWX.

Table 1. Auto Dock Vina docking results showing binding affinities of Ligands and Drug Molecules with PPAR δ protein (PDB Id: 1GWX)

S. No.	Ligand name	PubChem CID	Binding Affinity (ΔG) (kcal/mol)	No. of H-Bonds	H-Bond Forming Residues
1	C3G	441667	-8.8	4	Met228, Glu291, Thr292, Asn343
2	GW2433	1517	-8.4	4	Gly261, Thr288, Ala342, Ser345

Fig. 2a

Fig. 2b

Fig. 3a

Fig. 3b

Fig 2-3. (a) The 3D image shows significant interactions with donor and acceptor H –bonds regions **(b)** The molecular level interactions of binding–pocket residues with the molecules are depicted in the 2D plot.

3.2 Pharmacokinetics and ADMET Evaluation of ligand and GW2433

The Physico-chemical, pharmacokinetic and drug-likeness data are presented in Table 2 and Table 3. According to the pharmacokinetic/ADMET properties, ligand C3G and GW2433 molecule both showed low human intestinal absorption (HIA). Drug-likeness prediction was also performed for Lipinski, Ghose, Veber, Egan and Muegge. C3G showed better drug-likeness in comparison to GW2433 (Table 3, Fig 4).

Table 2. Predicted Physico-chemical and Molecular properties of ligands and GW2433

S/No.	Parameter	C3G	GW2433
1	Formula	C ₂₁ H ₂₁ O ₁₁ ⁺	C ₂₈ H ₂₈ Cl ₃ FN ₂ O ₄
2	Molecular weight	449.4 g/mol	581.89 g/mol
3	Num. heavy atoms	32	38
4	Num. arom. heavy atoms	16	18
5	Fraction Csp3	0.29	0.29
6	Num. rotatable bonds	4	13
7	Num. H-bond acceptors	11	5
8	Num. H-bond donors	8	2
9	Molar Refractivity	108.29	149.95
10	TPSA	193.44 Å ²	78.87
11	Log Po/w (iLOGP)	-2.48	4.21

Note: *HBA: Hydrogen Bond Acceptors (as total number of nitrogen and oxygen atoms),

**HBD: Hydrogen Bond Donors (as total number of oxygen–hydrogen and nitrogen–hydrogen bonds)

Table 3. In silico Pharmacokinetics, and Drug-likeness of studied Molecules

S/N	Pharmacokinetics			Drug-likeness (No. of violations)		
	Parameter	C3G	GW2433	Parameter	C3G	GW2433
1	GI absorption	Low	Low	Lipinski	No; 2	No; 2
2	BBB permeant	No	No	Ghose	Yes	No; 3

3	P-gp substrate	No	Yes	Veber	No; 1	No; 1
4	CYP1A2 inhibitor	No	No	Egan	No; 1	No; 1
5	CYP2C19 inhibitor	No	Yes	Muegge	No; 3	No; 1
6	CYP2C9 inhibitor	No	Yes	Leadlikeness	No; 1	No; 3
7	CYP2D6 inhibitor	No	Yes			
8	CYP3A4 inhibitor	No	No			
9	Log Kp (skin permeation)	-8.94 cm/s	-4.51 cm/s			

Fig. 4 Bioavailability radar of C3G and GW2433. The pink zone in the bioavailability radar is the ideal physicochemical space for oral bioavailability. LIPO (lipophilicity: $-0.7 < XLOGP3 < 5$); SIZE (molecular weight: $150 \text{ g/mol} < \text{mol wt} < 500 \text{ g/mol}$); POLAR (polarity: $20 \text{ \AA}^2 < \text{TPSA} < 140 \text{ \AA}^2$); INSOLU [insolubility: $0 < \text{Log S (ESOL)} < 6$]; INSATU (insaturation: $0.25 < \text{fraction C sp}^3 < 1$); and FLEX (flexibility: $0 < \text{number of rotatable bonds} < 9$).

Conclusions

Research on phytoconstituents seems to be a promising avenue given the severity of diabetes mellitus around the world and the adverse effects of current diabetes medications. The phytochemical cyanidin-3-O-glucoside was screened in this work with a focus on peroxisome proliferator-activated receptors (PPARs), particularly PPAR δ . These receptors are essential for controlling human glucose homeostasis, insulin sensitivity, and adipogenesis. In comparison to traditional PPAR δ agonists like GW2433, molecular docking analyses revealed that C3G has a higher binding affinity with the target protein. Given these results, it is reasonable to expect that C3G will show a safer and more potent antidiabetic medication. In order to validate this phytoconstituent's potential therapeutic effects for its incorporation into standard diabetes treatment regimens, it is imperative that it undergo rigorous clinical testing.

References :

1. WHO: Classification of diabetes mellitus, 2019, <https://apps.who.int/iris/handle/10665/325182>
2. IDF Diabetes Atlas 2025, <https://diabetesatlas.org/resources/idf-diabetes-atlas-2025/>
3. Groop, L.C., Widén, E. & Ferrannini, E. Insulin resistance and insulin deficiency in the pathogenesis of Type 2 (non-insulin-dependent) diabetes mellitus: errors of metabolism or of methods. *Diabetologia* 36, 1326–1331 (1993).
4. B. Lorenzati, C. Zucco, S. Miglietta, F. Lamberti, en G. Bruno, “Oral hypoglycemic drugs: Pathophysiological basis of their mechanism of action”, *Pharmaceuticals*, vol 3, no 9, bll 3005–3020, 2010, doi: 10.3390/ph3093005.
5. “American Diabetes Association, ‘Strategies for Improving Care,’ *Diabetes Care*, vol. 39, no. Supplement 1, p. S6, 2016, doi: 10.2337/dc16-S004”.
6. A. Moovenhan and L. Nivethitha, “A Narrative Review on Evidence-based Antidiabetic Effect of Fenu- greek (Trigonella Foenum-Graecum), <https://doi.org/10.4103/ijnpnd.ijnpnd>”, *Int J Nutr Pharmacol Neurol Dis.*, vol 7, bll 84–87, 2017.

7. A. Mooventhana and L. Nivethitha, “A Narrative Review on Evidence-based Antidiabetic Effect of Fenugreek (*Trigonella Foenum-Graccum*), <https://doi.org/10.4103/ijnpnd.ijnpnd>”, *Int J Nutr Pharmacol Neurol Dis.*, vol 7, bl 84–87, 2017.
8. S. Roychoudhury, B. Sinha, B.P. Choudhury, N.K. Jha, P. Palit, S. Kundu, et al. Scavenging properties of plant-derived natural biomolecule para-coumaric acid in the prevention of oxidative stress-induced diseases. *Antioxidants.* (2021) 10:1205. doi: 10.3390/antiox10081205
9. A. Visen, S. Visen, A. Sharma, PKS Visen. Chapter 40 – Nutraceuticals as a natural alternative for preventive and proactive health care. In: RB Singh, S Watanabe, AA Isaza Editors. *Functional foods and nutraceuticals in metabolic and non-communicable diseases.* Cambridge, MA: Academic Press (2022) p. 603–18. doi: 10.1016/B978-0-12-819815-5.00040-9
10. Christofides, A., Konstantinidou, E., Jani, C. & Boussiotis, V.A. The role of peroxisome proliferators-activated receptors (PPAR) in immune responses. *Metab. Clin. Exp.* 114, 154338 (2021).
11. Lee, C.H., et al. PPAR delta regulates glucose metabolism and insulin sensitivity. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. USA* 103, 3444–3449 (2006).
12. Chang, J.T., Liang, Y.J. & Leu, J.G. Glucagon-like peptide-1 receptor regulates receptor of advanced glycation end products in high glucose-treated rat mesangial cells. *J. Chin. Med. Assoc.* 86, 39–46 (2023).
13. Chon, S. & Gautier, J. F. An update on the effect of incretin-based therapies on β -cell function and mass. *Diabetes Metab. J.* 40, 99–114 (2016).
14. Andersen, A., Lund, A. & Knop, F. K. Vilsbøll T. Glucagon-like peptide 1 in health and disease. *Nat. Rev. Endocrinol.* 14, 390–403 (2018).
15. In Silico Characterization of a Novel Bioactive Compound derived from *Psidium guajava* 4-[5-(Pyridin-4-yl)-1,2,4-oxadiazol-3-yl]-1,2,5-oxadiazol-3-amine: A Potential Inhibitor for Targeting Signaling Proteins involved in Diabetes Development. *Int. J. Pharm. Sci. Drug Res.* 2024;16(2):180-9. Available from: <https://ijpsdronline.com/index.php/journal/article/view/8584>
16. Maya, Raj KS Yadav. Molecular Docking and ADMET Profiling of Novel Human Dipeptidyl Peptidase-IV Inhibitors of Natural Origin from *Dalbergia sissoo*: In Silico Prediction in Antidiabetic Potential. *Int. J. Pharm. Sci. Drug Res.* 2024; 16(5):841-54. Available from: <https://ijpsdronline.com/index.php/journal/article/view/9988>
17. Tian, L. et al. Dietary cyanidin-3-glucoside attenuates high-fatdiet– induced body-weight gain and impairment of glucose tolerance in mice via effects on the hepatic hormone FGF21. *J. Nutr.* 150, 2101–2111 (2020).
18. Qi, S.S. et al. Cyanidin-3-glucoside from black rice prevents renal dysfunction and renal fibrosis in streptozotocin-diabetic rats. *J. Funct. Foods* 72, 104062 (2020).
19. Guillermo Cásedas, Francisco Les, Elena González-Burgos, Maria Pilar Gómez- Serranillos, Carine Smith, Víctor López, Cyanidin-3-O-glucoside inhibits different enzymes involved in central nervous system pathologies and type-2 diabetes, *South African Journal of Botany*, Volume 120, 2019, Pages 241-246, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sajb.2018.07.001>.
20. “Protein Data Bank”. [Online]. Available at: <https://www.rcsb.org/>
21. “BIOVIA, Dassault Systèmes, Discovery Studio, 2021, San Diego: Dassault Systèmes, 2021. - Google Search”. [Online]. Available at: <https://discover.3ds.com/discovery-studio-visualizer>
22. Dallakyan S, Olson AJ. Small-Molecule Library Screening by Docking with PyRx. *Methods Mol Biol.* 2015; 1263:243-50
23. “PubChem Data Bank”. [Online]. Available at: <https://pubchem.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/>
24. “SwissADME”. Toegang verkry: 24 November 2023. [Online]. Available at: <http://www.swissadme.ch/>
25. C.A. Lipinski, F. Lombardo, B.W. Dominy, en P.J. Feeney, “Experimental and computational approaches to estimate solubility and permeability in drug discovery and development settings”, *Advanced Drug Delivery Reviews*, vol. 64, no SUPPL., bl 4–17, 2012, doi: 10.1016/j.addr.2012.09.019.

